

Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy Among Social Studies Teacher-Trainees at the University of Education, Winneba, Ghana

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ABSTRACT: This study examined the level of entrepreneurial self-efficacy among undergraduate teacher-trainees in the Department of Social Studies Education at the University of Education, Winneba. The mixed methods approach at a convergent parallel was used for the study. The sample size for the study was seven hundred and fifty (750) participants who were selected by census. Twenty-one (21) respondents out of the 750 were selected conveniently for the qualitative data. The instruments used for gathering data included a questionnaire and an interview guide for the quantitative and qualitative data, respectively. The quantitative data were analysed through the generation of descriptive statistics in the form of frequencies, means, percentages, and standard deviations. The qualitative data were analysed under various themes generated from the data gathered. Findings from the study indicate that Social Studies undergraduate teacher-trainees of the University of Education, Winneba, possess high levels of entrepreneurial self-efficacy. It was therefore recommended that the government create an enabling environment that would allow these undergraduate teacher-trainees to pursue their entrepreneurial dreams after school.

KEYWORDS: Undergraduate teacher-trainee, entrepreneurship, entrepreneurial self-efficacy, employability skills, entrepreneurial intentions

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I. INTRODUCTION

As a programme of study that aims at preparing learners with the competences to fit in the ever-changing glocal society with its attendant emanating issues, Social Studies is replete with courses that are meant to prepare learners to solve emanating issues within the society, of which graduate unemployment is not an exception. To deal with the issue of unemployment, entrepreneurship as a course is taught in the Department of Social Studies Education of the University of Education, Winneba, to acquaint learners with the knowledge, skills, entrepreneurial attitudes, and values that are germane in starting and managing one's own business without necessarily relying on anyone for employment after school. This is a deliberate attempt to prepare learners to become self-reliant, independent thinkers, job creators rather than job seekers, persons who will teach to also develop in their learners, entrepreneurial and employability skills (as relevant 21st century skills), and individuals who are generally capable of solving their personal problems and other societal issues of human survival. Hasyim et al. (2024:2) argue that "one of the causes of the lack of employment for those who have graduated from college or have a bachelor's degree is that many graduates only aim to find work, not create new jobs." Researchers maintain that the most viable ways of solving the problem of graduate unemployment in evolving economies is through entrepreneurship (Bektas, 2011; Von Broembsen et al., 2005; Haftendorn & Salzano, 2003; Lee et al., 2015 as cited in Poatob, 2024). Entrepreneurship not only creates jobs for the initiators but also serves as an avenue through which multitudes get employed. It also has a ripple effect on the economic growth, higher national incomes and the general improvement in the standard of living of citizens in the society. Entrepreneurship has the tendency to turn an agrarian economy into an industrial or quasi-industrial economy.

Teaching entrepreneurship as a course of study is one thing, and assimilating and being willing to put into practice what has been taught is another thing that demands attention. This statement is akin to what the Bible says in the book of Ezekiel chapter 33 verse 31 (Ezekiel 33:31—King James Version) "And they come unto thee as the people cometh, and they sit before thee as my people, and they hear the words, but they will not do them: for with their mouth they show much love, but their heart goeth after their

covetousness.” This implies that teachers and researchers have a responsibility to make follow-ups to see how learners respond or react to what is taught in class. These follow-ups must be at different stages. For instance, the first stage is to explore their level of appreciation of what is taught and their willingness to implement, the second stage is to follow-up to see whether they have really implemented what was learnt, and the third stage is to follow-up to see if the knowledge and skills received and implemented are still functional and therefore, making them to succeed in their entrepreneurial endeavours. Not until these are done will it be difficult to evaluate the relevance of a programme or course of study. This study sought to explore the first stage to see Social Studies teacher-trainees’ level of self-efficacy and willingness, which serve as a basis for further follow-up research.

Earlier studies on Social Studies students' entrepreneurial intentions (Poatob, 2024) and their entrepreneurial knowledge (Poatob et al., 2025) in Ghana show that students have high levels of entrepreneurial intentions and knowledge, respectively. This current study aims at determining the level of entrepreneurial self-efficacy—the belief or confidence Social Studies undergraduates have in their competencies that they can start and manage their own businesses after school (Slavec & Prodan, 2012). Many people do not venture into entrepreneurship because they do not have the confidence that they have what it takes to succeed in that endeavour. This makes them risk-averse with the mindset of ‘what if it doesn’t work?’ Though individuals may have the requisite knowledge, values, and skills needed to become successful entrepreneurs, their level of self-efficacy is what will determine whether they will venture into entrepreneurship as a career option or rely on others for employment after school. It is this bedrock that necessitated this current study. The study was guided by the following main research question:

What is the entrepreneurial self-efficacy level of undergraduate teacher-trainees in the Department of Social Studies Education at the University of Education, Winneba, in starting and managing their own businesses?

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Entrepreneurial self-efficacy

The history of self-efficacy began with Bandura (1977). social learning theory, which was renamed social cognitive theory in 1986. One of Bandura’s major concepts in his theory was self-efficacy. According to Bandura (1995), self-efficacy makes a difference in how people feel, think, behave, and motivate themselves. When it comes to feeling, a low sense of self-efficacy is associated with stress, depression, anxiety, and helplessness. Such individuals also have low self-esteem and become pessimistic about their accomplishments and personal development. In terms of thinking, a strong sense of efficacy facilitates cognitive processes and performance across a variety of settings, including decision quality and academic achievement. Self-efficacy levels can increase or hamper motivation. People with high self-efficacy approach difficult tasks as challenges and do not try to avoid them. “People’s self-efficacy beliefs shape their level of motivation, as reflected in how much effort they will exert in an endeavor and how long they will persevere in the face of obstacles (Bandura, 1989).

Self-efficacy is viewed as beliefs that function as an important set of proximal determinants of human motivation and action (Bandura, 1989, 1986) and that those beliefs constitute a form of action through motivational, cognitive, and affective intervening processes. One of the cognitive processes is setting personal goals. Hence, the higher the level of perceived self-efficacy, the higher the levels of goals people set for themselves, and thus, a higher level of commitment to the goals. What this means is that individuals with a higher level of self-efficacy are more likely to be enterprising than those with a low level of self-efficacy.

Entrepreneurial self-efficacy has been defined by Campo (2011) as the extent to which one believes that they can successfully start a new business venture. It is the belief in one’s own capabilities to take-action on defined goals (Bandura, 1984) Entrepreneurial self-efficacy has been seen to play a key role in determining the level of interest in pursuing an entrepreneurial career (Segal, Borgia, & Schoenfeld, 2005; Wilson, Kickul & Marlino, 2007) and is therefore viewed as having the capabilities that can modify a person’s belief in his or her completing the tasks required to successfully initiate and establish a new business venture [4] Solesvik, 2007; Nabi, Holden & Walmsley, 2010; Rae & Woodier-Harris, 2013; Olakitan, 2014). It is said that the key drivers of intention and performance, as researched in past studies, include entrepreneurial education (Bae, et al., 2014) entrepreneurial self-efficacy and cultural environment (Hopp & Stephan, 2012), among which entrepreneurial self-efficacy is highly critical for business accomplishment (Rauch & Frese, 2007).

Several research works have ascertained entrepreneurial self-efficacy as a strong driver of entrepreneurial behaviour (Cromie, 2000; Drnovsek, Wincent & Cardon, 2010; Markman, Balkin & Baron, 2002; Nwankwo, et al., 2012, Okunloye & Obeng, 2013, Okunloye, 2024) and is expected to influence choices, goals, emotions, efforts, reactions, ability to cope, and persistence (Gist, Stevens & Bavetta, 1991) which are crucial for entrepreneurial success. According to Zhao, Seibert and Hills (2005) and Carr and Sequeira (2007), increased self-efficacy yields greater entrepreneurial intentions. Consequently, entrepreneurial self-efficacy has been identified as an important antecedent of entrepreneurial career (Barbosa, Gerhardt, & Kickul, 2007; Linan, Rodriguez- Cohard & Rueda-Cantuche, 2005; Mushtaq, Hunjra, Niazi, Rehman & Azam, 2011; Pruett, Shinnar, Toney, Llopis & Fox, 2009; Rae & Woodier-Harris, 2013; Smith & Beasley, 2011; Souitaris, Zerbinati & Al-Laham, 2007; Zhao, Scott & Hills, 2005). This is because entrepreneurial self-efficacy has been empirically tested and found to associate positively with entrepreneurial career in several studies (Chen, Greene & Crick, 1998; Douglas & Shepherd, 2002; Krueger, Reilly & Carsrud, 2000). A higher level of self-efficacy

is associated with entrepreneurship and new venture creation (Frazier & Niehm, 2006; Krueger & Brazeal, 1994; Segal, Borgia & Schoenfeld, 2005).

[5] posits that “human behavior is regulated by forethought embodying cognised goals, and personal goal setting is influenced by self-appraisal of capabilities”. People with high levels of self-efficacy are more likely to set higher goals, commit to challenges that are more difficult, and strive to meet those goals. They achieve the goals by visualising successful outcomes instead of dwelling on the potential negative consequences. “A major function of thought is to enable people to predict the occurrence of events and to create the avenue for exercising control over those that affect their daily lives (Bandura et al., 1997; Bandura, 1985), which is a key component of self-efficacy.

According to Bandura (1994), a strong sense of efficacy enhances human accomplishment and personal well-being in many ways. Individuals with high assurance in their capabilities approach difficult tasks as challenges to be mastered rather than as threats to be avoided. Such an effective outlook fosters intrinsic interest and deep engrossment in activities. They set themselves challenging goals and maintain a strong commitment to them. They heighten and sustain their efforts in the face of failure. They quickly recover their sense of efficacy after failures or setbacks. They attribute failure to insufficient effort or deficient knowledge and skills, which are acquirable. They approach threatening situations with assurance that they can exercise control over them. Such an efficacious outlook produces personal accomplishments, reduces stress and lowers vulnerability to depression.

On the contrary, individuals who doubt their capabilities often shy away from difficult tasks, which they view as personal threats. They have low aspirations and weak commitment to the goals they choose to pursue. When faced with difficult tasks, they dwell on their personal deficiencies, on the obstacles they will encounter, and all kinds of adverse outcomes rather than concentrate on how to perform successfully. They slacken their efforts and give up quickly in the face of difficulties. They are slow to recover their sense of efficacy following failure or setbacks. Because they view insufficient performance as deficient aptitude, and it does not require much failure for them to lose faith in their capabilities. They fall easy victim to stress and depression. Self-efficacy is defined as a person’s own judgment of the capabilities to perform a certain activity to attain a certain outcome (Zulkosky, 2009).

In an entrepreneurial context, self-efficacy can be defined as people’s confidence in their ability to succeed in entrepreneurial roles and tasks (Chen et al., 1998). Entrepreneurial self-efficacy is what influences choices, aspirations, and effort, in addition to perseverance when entrepreneurs face difficulties (Boyd & Vozikis, 1994), and it plays an essential role in the development of an intention to establish and manage a new venture (Kickul et al., 2008; Mueller & Dato-On, 2008). Some researchers have particularly focused on whether self-efficacy is a key factor in explaining why some individuals are motivated to become entrepreneurs and others are not (Wilson et al., 2009; Zhao et al., 2005). In this regard, the research has shown compelling and consistent patterns, reflecting that individuals with higher entrepreneurial self-efficacy tend to exhibit higher entrepreneurial intention (Chen et al., 1998; Kickul et al., 2008; Wang et al., 2002). This current study seeks to either confirm or disprove the findings of past studies on the influence of self-efficacy on the decision of individuals to become entrepreneurs when it comes to teacher-trainees at the Department of Social Studies Education in the University of Education, Winneba.

Some incipient researchers have analysed data on entrepreneurial self-efficacy and entrepreneurial intention from a gender perspective (Kirkwood, 2009; Lavolette et al., 2012; Wilson et al., 2007; Zhao et al., 2005), and the little empirical evidence suggests that a higher proportion of women than men reject the choice of an entrepreneurial career and involvement in entrepreneurial activities because they perceive themselves as lacking the necessary abilities (Chen et al., 1998; Kickul et al., 2008; Wilson et al., 2007). This means that the level of self-efficacy of men is found to be higher than that of women, resulting in men wanting to engage in entrepreneurial activities more than women. Following the main premises of Social Feminist Theory, women may identify themselves as less effective than men in their business abilities because they are less likely to be socialised in business roles and to be confronted with expectations for starting a business (Kalleberg & Leicht, 1991; Yordanova & Tarrazon, 2010).

Some studies also cited that differential access to opportunities and resources could culminate in women being disadvantaged in terms of previous managerial experience and training, and as a result, women could feel that they lack the requisite abilities for entrepreneurship (Verheul et al., 2005; Yordanova & Tarrazon, 2010). Similarly, self-efficacy has been considered by Kickul et al (2008) as an important element in the consideration of entrepreneurship as a professional career and women more often than not limit their options in career selection because of a perception that they lack abilities they consider necessary for entrepreneurial careers. Wilson et al (2007) in their study found empirical evidence that both female adolescents and MBA students exhibited lower rates of entrepreneurial self-efficacy and entrepreneurial intention than their female counterparts. [6] however, noted that when women get involved in the development of entrepreneurial activities, it significantly increases their perceptions regarding their entrepreneurial abilities in such a way that gender differences in entrepreneurial intention could be by the impact of entrepreneurial self-efficacy.

Following Bandura’s position, Cox et al. (2002) pointed out that “mastery experiences or simply put ‘learning by doing’, appear to be basic in determining our self-confidence to successfully perform future tasks that are perceived to be similar or related” (Wilson et al., 2007: 392). This is because when women become entrepreneurs, they can acquire social, cognitive and language abilities through business experiences, workshops, or entrepreneurial training, which may increase their levels of entrepreneurial self-efficacy and reach similar levels as those of men (Kirkwood, 2009; Wilson et al., 2007). A study conducted on the mediating role

of entrepreneurial self-efficacy on the relationship between gender and entrepreneurial intention of students and early career adults found that entrepreneurial self-efficacy partially mediated such relationships in both cases (Wilson et al., 2009).

2.2. Sources of self-efficacy

According to Bandura (1994), individuals' beliefs about their self-efficacy can be developed by four main sources of influence. The first and most effective one is mastery of experience (performance accomplishment). People become self-confident when they have gathered enough experiences and understand the intricacies of what they do. With these experiences, such individuals exhibit a very high level of self-efficacy. According to Bandura (1994), when people experience only easy successes, they come to expect quick results and are easily discouraged by failure. A resilient sense of efficacy requires experience in overcoming obstacles through perseverant effort. Some setbacks and difficulties in human pursuits serve a useful purpose in teaching that success usually requires sustained effort. After people become convinced that they have what it takes to succeed, they persevere in the face of adversity and quickly bounce back from setbacks. By sticking it out through tough times, they emerge stronger from adversity.

The second way of creating and strengthening self-beliefs of efficacy, according to Bandura (1994), is through the vicarious experiences provided by social models. Seeing people similar to oneself succeed by sustained effort raises observers' beliefs that they too possess the capabilities to learn comparable activities to succeed. In the same way, observing others' failure despite high effort lowers observers' judgments of their own efficacy and undermines their efforts. The impact of modeling on perceived self-efficacy is strongly influenced by perceived similarity to the models. The greater the assumed similarity, the more persuasive the models' successes and failures are in affecting the self-efficacy of the observer. If people see the models as very different from themselves, their perceived self-efficacy is not much influenced by the models' behavior and the results it produces. Modeling influences usually do more than provide a social standard against which to judge one's own capabilities. People seek proficient models who possess the competencies to which they aspire. Through their behaviour and expressed ways of thinking, competent models transmit knowledge and teach observers effective skills and strategies for managing environmental demands.

The third factor to consider is Social Persuasion (verbal persuasion). Social persuasion is one of the ways Bandura (1994) admitted could strengthen people's beliefs that they have what it takes to succeed. For instance, people who are persuaded verbally that they possess the capabilities to master given activities are likely to mobilise greater effort and sustain it than if they harbor self-doubts and dwell on personal deficiencies when problems arise. Persuasiveness, therefore, boosts the perceived self-efficacy in people and leads them to try hard enough to succeed, thereby promoting the development of skills and a sense of personal efficacy.

Lastly, individuals also rely partly on their somatic and emotional states in judging their capabilities. They interpret their stress reactions and tension as signs of vulnerability to poor performance. In activities involving strength and stamina, people judge their fatigue, aches, and pains as signs of physical debility. Mood also affects people's judgments of their personal efficacy. Positive mood enhances perceived self-efficacy, but a despondent mood diminishes it. The fourth way of modifying self-beliefs of efficacy, therefore, is to reduce people's stress reactions and alter their negative emotional proclivities and misinterpretations of their physical states.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study employed a convergent parallel mixed methods design, which enabled us to merge quantitative and qualitative data to provide a comprehensive analysis of the research problem (Creswell, 2018). Both qualitative and quantitative forms of data were collected simultaneously, analysed separately, and then integrated during interpretation. The population for the study comprised all seven hundred and fifty (750) Level 300 Major and Minor Social Studies students offering entrepreneurship-related courses in the Department of Social Studies Education at the University of Education, Winneba (UEW) during the 2018/2019 Academic Year. As a result of this, all the level 300 major and minor students are offering such a course(s). Though the data were collected before the COVID-19 pandemic, the findings remain significant on the grounds that the entrepreneurial self-efficacy, comparably, represents a stable psychological construct that evolves for sustained periods within educational contexts [3]. Besides, the structure of the Bachelor of Arts in Social Studies programme, especially the programme's curriculum and heutagogical approaches have remained largely unchanged, making the 2019 data a replication of ongoing practices.

Whereas a comprehensive (census) sampling technique was used to sample respondents for collecting the quantitative data, a total of twenty-one (21) participants were conveniently selected for the qualitative data (interviews). Both the researcher-developed questionnaire and interview guide were developed and used as instruments for gathering data for the study based on a careful literature review. The blend of several data collection methods allowed for data triangulation as supported by Creswell (2018). In effect, the data triangulation offered us the opportunity to confirm evidence from different sources to shed light on a particular phenomenon or issue. In addition, each instrument was used to offset the weakness of the other.

Methodological rigour of our study was attained through the process of legitimation typology as opined by Onwuegbuzie and Johnson (2006); Onwuegbuzie and Burke (2007); Onwuegbuzie (2012) and Johnson and Christensen (2017). In the context of our study, the typologies of sample legitimation, weakness minimisation, data conversion, pragmatic mixing and multiple validities were used as more applicable typologies to address issues of validity, reliability, credibility and trustworthiness. This was done while maintaining philosophical coherence via pragmatism, which reconciled competing methodological approaches.

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For instance, weakness minimisation was established through the offsetting limitations of the questionnaire with strengths of the interview, experts' review for content validity, and Cronbach's alpha was used, which produced a coefficient of 0.84 for internal consistency, and peer-debriefing increased reliability. For sample integration, the 21 interview participants had also completed the questionnaire. This assured a direct comparison between qualitative and quantitative results from the same individuals. On the typology of emic (inside)-etic (outside) legitimation, there was the need to balance the insider and outsider perspectives by maintaining objectivity during the point of administering the questionnaire while taking a subjective stance during the interviews. This was supported by member checking, reflexive journaling, and triangulation with both primary and secondary data. Additionally, multiple validities considered method-specific validity. Thus, content validity for questionnaires and trustworthiness for quantitative and qualitative data, respectively, political legitimation considered power differences between us as researchers and the participants/respondents. It further considered how the findings could be of significance to various actors in teacher education. Lastly, conversion legitimation was addressed by appropriately quantising qualitative data and qualitisng quantitative data. This was done through the adequate capturing of meaningful results and transforming themes into measurable variables. Whereas quantitative data analysis was done through descriptive statistics, which were generated using SPSS, qualitative data was transcribed, scrutinised for recurring patterns and themes as corroborated by Bogdan and Biklen (2007), and integrated during data discussion to make more meaning as confirmed by Poatob et al. (2025). Ethical considerations involved obtaining participants/respondents' consent, ensuring voluntary participation, ensuring anonymity and confidentiality using pseudonyms. Also, recorded videos and audios were secured with colleague lecturers and research assistants tasked to minimise emic bias and conflict of interest.

IV. RESULTS

The research question sought to assess the entrepreneurial self-efficacy level of undergraduate university students, and both quantitative and qualitative data were gathered in an attempt to answer it. The quantitative and qualitative findings that sought to answer this question are presented as follows, per the dictates of the convergent parallel mixed methods design.

4.1. Quantitative Results

Descriptive statistics were used to present the quantitative findings. Presented in Table 1 are the descriptive statistics of the entrepreneurial self-efficacy level of undergraduate students of the University of Education, Winneba, are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy of Undergraduate Teacher-Trainees

	Entrepreneurial Self-efficacy	D (%)	A (%)	M	Std.
1	I will be able to achieve most of the goals that I have set for myself when I become an entrepreneur	61(8.2)	686(91.8)	2.9	0.2
2	I have the ability to start a business and keep it working and running easily	54(7.2)	695(92.8)	2.9	0.2
3	When facing difficult tasks, I am certain that I will accomplish them.	40(5.3)	708(94.7)	2.9	0.2
4	I can do the creation process of a new business all by myself	252(33.9)	491(66.1)	2.6	0.4
5	In general, I think that I can obtain outcomes that are important to me.	52(7.0)	694(93.0)	2.9	0.2
6	I believe I know the practical details of a new business	176(23.8)	565(76.2)	2.7	0.4
7	I believe I can succeed at any endeavor to which I set my mind on	67(9.0)	679(91.0)	2.9	0.2
8	If I tried a business, I would have a high probability of success	68(9.2)	675(90.8)	2.9	0.2
9	I will be able to successfully overcome many challenges faced as an entrepreneur.	52(6.9)	697(93.1)	2.9	0.2
10	I am confident that I can perform effectively on many different tasks regarding the business I intend to start.	45(6.0)	704(94.0)	2.9	0.2
11	I certainly know how to develop an entrepreneurial project	162(21.7)	586(78.3)	2.7	0.4
12	Compared to other people, I can do most tasks very well	57(7.7)	687(92.3)	2.9	0.2
13	Even when things are tough, I can perform quite well	46(6.2)	700(93.8)	2.9	0.2
14	I am capable of solving daily business problems	74(10.0)	663(90.0)	2.9	0.3
15	Thanks to my resourcefulness, I know how to manage money judiciously	52(7.0)	696(93.0)	2.9	0.2
16	If someone opposes me, I can find the means and ways of getting him/her to agree with me	43(5.8)	704(94.2)	2.9	0.2
17	I have the ability to become a great leader	10(1.3)	738(98.7)	2.9	0.1
18	I can usually handle whatever comes my way by making good decisions	21(2.8)	725(97.2)	2.9	0.1

Source: Field Data (2019)

Note: D= Disagree; A=Agree; M=Mean; Std=Standard Deviation

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Analysis of data on the research question indicates how mature or otherwise undergraduate students of the Department of Social Studies Education, University of Education, Winneba, were in terms of entrepreneurial self-efficacy. Responses to the research question were varied. Results as presented in Table 1 on the entrepreneurial self-efficacy level indicate that overall, the respondents had adequate maturity levels. From the descriptive statistics shown in Table 1, the mean scores on all the items were greater than 2.5. The results indicate that the majority of the respondents would be able to achieve most of the goals that they had set for themselves as entrepreneurs when they become business people ($n = 686, 91.8\%, M = 2.9$ and $Std. = 0.2$). The analysis again illustrates that most of the respondents indicated that they could start a business and keep it working and running easily ($n = 695, 92.8\%, M = 2.9$ and $Std. = 0.2$). Research results from the undergraduate students, as presented in Table 1, indicated that the majority of them would be able to accomplish a difficult task when facing it ($n = 708, 94.8\%, M = 2.9$ and $Std. = 0.2$). Similarly, the results indicated that the respondents were mature enough to create a process for a new business all by themselves ($n = 491, 66.1\%, M = 2.6$ and $Std. = 0.4$). The result further revealed that an overwhelming majority of the respondents would be able to obtain outcomes that were important to them ($n = 694, 93.0\%, M = 2.9$ and $Std. = 0.2$).

Besides, the results obtained indicated that 565 (76.2%) of the respondents believed they knew the practical details of a new business. In the same regard, most of the students indicated that they believed they could succeed at any endeavor to which they set their mind on ($n = 679, 91.0\%, M = 2.9$ and $Std. = 0.2$). Research results in Table 1 further suggest that the majority of the students were mature enough that if they tried a business, they would have a high probability of success ($n = 675, 90.8\%$). It must also be stated that the majority of the students indicated that they would be able to successfully overcome most challenges they anticipate facing as an entrepreneur ($n = 697, 93.1\%$). The results, as shown in Table 1, additionally indicated that the students were mature enough to possess the confidence that they could perform effectively on many different tasks regarding the business they intend to start ($n = 704, 94.0\%$). Most of the participants were also certain they had the skills to know how to develop an entrepreneurial project ($n = 586, 78.3\%, M = 2.7$ and $Std. = 0.4$).

The results from Table 1 further signified that the students were mature enough to compare themselves to other people and know that they could perform most tasks creditably well ($n = 687, 92.3\%, M = 2.9$ and $Std. = 0.2$). It also came to the fore that most of the respondents indicated that when things got tough, they could still perform quite well ($n = 700, 93.8\%, M = 2.9$ and $Std. = 0.2$). It can be seen that most of the undergraduate teacher-trainees in the Department of Social Studies Education were capable of solving daily business problems that they may face in the near future ($n = 663, 90.0\%, M = 2.9$ and $Std. = 0.3$). In the same regard, the student teachers revealed that they could manage money judiciously due to their resourcefulness ($n = 696, 93.0\%, M = 2.9$ and $Std. = 0.2$). Research results as presented in Table 1 further indicated that the majority of them opposed them; they could find the means and ways of getting them to agree with them ($n = 704, 94.2\%, M = 2.9$ and $Std. = 0.2$). The outcome from the current study further indicated that the students were very certain and optimistic that they had the ability to become great leaders in the near future in the world of business ($n = 738, 98.7\%, M = 2.9$ and $Std. = 0.1$). Finally, most of the participants indicated that they could handle whatever comes their way by making good decisions concerning their future entrepreneurship ventures ($n = 725, 97.2\%, M = 2.9$ and $Std. = 0.1$).

4.2. Qualitative Results

Similar to how the quantitative findings are presented, the qualitative findings on entrepreneurial self-efficacy are presented employing thematic analysis of participant interviews. The thematic analysis is done based on the primary source(s) of self-efficacy expressed regarding participants' ability to start and manage their own businesses. Following are the details of the presentation of the findings.

4.2.1. Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy

The level of confidence is very important in entrepreneurial success. In view of this, we elicited from the respondents how confident they were regarding their ability to start and manage their own businesses. The question asked was "Are you confident that you can start and manage your own business? If yes, what makes you confident?" In responding to the questions above, Ama said:

Yes, I know I can succeed in setting up my own business because my siblings are already in it and they have given me the zeal and perhaps they are there to help and support me."

Similarly, Esi asserted:

Yes, in the sense that while someone has succeeded, I wish to fight till I reach my highest peak and be counted as one of such successful ones.

The two respondents (Ama and Esi) were confident that they could start and manage their own businesses because they have observed people in their neighbourhood who have started their own businesses and have succeeded and so they take inspiration from that and have the confidence that they too can succeed. This tells us the importance of role models and mentors in entrepreneurial success.

The next group of respondents were those who either started their own businesses and worked for some time and came to school, or worked for someone else and have built up a high level of confidence as a result of their earlier experiences. In responding to the question on their level of confidence in starting and managing their own businesses, Kwame said:

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Yes, because I have worked with my uncle who is a great farmer who has been able to make it through farming.

Similarly, Kofi said:

Yes. I have had the opportunity to establish a business for three good years before school which has really given me the experience on how to manage a business efficiently.

In the same vein, Kwakye said:

I have confidence to manage my business because I have assisted my father to sell drugs since the year 2008, so I can succeed if I start my business.

The confidence of the two respondents (Kofi and Kwakye) may have been reinforced by their past business experiences. Having been involved in either working for their parents or their own small businesses, they were very confident that they could start and manage their businesses after school. Their experiences were primary experiences that developed their abilities and gave them the needed confidence. It is imperative to highlight the importance of past experience in boosting the confidence of employees. It is not without reason that employers sometimes look for employees with many years of experience so that they can bring the plethora of experiences to bear in the job they are employed to do.

The third group of respondents was those who believe in their abilities and the skills they have attained either through formal, informal or non-formal education. The majority of the respondents fell in this third group. One of the respondents (Afia) in this group said:

Yes, because I am a goal achiever and also have good entrepreneurship skills with a lot of motivation from family and friends.

To her, she has the skills needed to succeed as an entrepreneur, and with motivation from friends and family members, she was confident she could succeed when she started her own business.

Similarly, Abena said:

Yes, because I have the passion to start my own business and I listen to lectures given by business tycoons who started from scratch and are now big women and men. I think their stories can motivate me to be able to manage my own business.

In the same way, Kojo said:

Yes. I have knowledge of entrepreneurship and I am also taking advice and learning from my well-established counterparts which gives me the zeal that I can do.

One other respondent (Afi) said:

Yes. Because I have good interpersonal relationships, I'm smart and hardworking. I am also able to identify problems easily and find solutions to them.

In like manner, Mike said:

Yes, I am confident because I have the motivation and critical thinking skills to deal with risks.

In response to the same question, Ntebi said:

Yes, because of some qualities I possess within me, I can establish and manage my own business.

Esther in her response to the same question, said:

Yes, because through the entrepreneurship course, I have gotten to know what it takes for one to succeed as an entrepreneur, which I believe I can also succeed.

For this group of respondents, their self-efficacy stems from the fact that they have the skills needed and the motivation from others with entrepreneurial experiences.

V. DISCUSSION

[3] defined self-efficacy as “beliefs in one’s capabilities to organize and execute the courses of action required to produce given attainments” (p. 3). In an entrepreneurial context, entrepreneurial self-efficacy is defined as an individual’s confidence in his/her ability to succeed in entrepreneurial roles and tasks (Slavec & Prodan, 2012). The assertion is that the higher the entrepreneurial self-efficacy, the higher the entrepreneurial success one is expected to achieve. Therefore, this research question sought to assess the entrepreneurial self-efficacy level of undergraduate teacher-trainees in the Department of Social Studies Education at the University of Education, Winneba, in starting and managing their own business. The results indicated that the respondents had high entrepreneurial self-efficacy and confidence in starting and managing their own business. This indicated that the respondents were mature enough to start and manage their own business. Specifically, it was found that most of the respondents indicated that they would be able to achieve most of the goals that they set for themselves as entrepreneurs; they also intimated that they can start a business and keep it working and running easily.

Again, the majority of them indicated that they were mature enough that if they tried a business, they would have a high probability of success. It was also found that the majority of the students indicated that they would be able to successfully overcome most challenges they anticipate facing as entrepreneurs. The results from the current study additionally indicated that the students were

mature enough to possess the confidence that they could perform effectively on many different tasks regarding the business they intend to start. Most of the participants were also certain they had the knowledge and skills of developing an entrepreneurial project. The findings from the table further signified that the students were mature enough to compare themselves to other people and know that they could perform most tasks creditably well. These findings and many more proved that the respondents were having high entrepreneurial self-efficacy level.

The findings concur with other researchers who affirmed entrepreneurial self-efficacy as a strong driver of entrepreneurial behaviour (Cromie, 2000; Drnoviaek, Wincent & Cardon, 2010; Markman, Balkin & Baron, 2002; Nwankwo, Kanu, Marire, Balogun & Uhiara, 2012) and is expected to influence choices, goals, emotions, efforts, reactions, ability to cope and persistence in entrepreneurial activities (Gist, Stevens & Bavetta, 1991). This is because this study showed that the respondents had a higher level of entrepreneurial self-efficacy, which had a greater influence on their entrepreneurial intentions. (Okunloye & Obeng, 2013; Okunloye, 2024).

VI. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1. Conclusion

It was concluded that in the light of the undergraduate teacher-trainees' high level of entrepreneurship self-efficacy, University Undergraduates in Education Faculties have a greater propensity to engage and succeed in post-graduate entrepreneurial ventures and engagements. Accordingly, students' formative experiences in Teacher Education Curricula is a significant and viable option for tackling graduate unemployment in Ghana.

6.2. Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn, we recommend that the government of Ghana create an enabling environment where there is security, stability, low interest rates on borrowing, and access to credit facilities, among others, to aid these potential entrepreneurs in putting into action their entrepreneurial ambitions. In addition, the University, in collaboration with the Ghana Tertiary Education Commission (GTEC), should leverage on the observed undergraduate teacher-trainees' high entrepreneurial self-efficacy by introducing Entrepreneurship-related enrichment curriculum in the existing teacher education curricula in all universities offering Bachelor's Degree Programmes of studies.

Although the study provides significant insights into entrepreneurial self-efficacy among Social Studies teacher-trainees, its findings are constrained by its single-institutional scope, convenience sampling for the qualitative strand, and its reliance on self-reported measures/questionnaires prone to response bias.

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